

The Critical Analysis of Prana in Upanishads

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Abstract

Energy is termed as the basic fabric of everything in the physical world. The science has explored in its deeper level to unfold the secrets of life, and succeeded in it. Therefore, the physical world is well understood. The 'prana' works as subtle energy and vital force in universe. Science is totally involved in investigating the energy present in the universe. Its investigation gets restricted due to the sense perception. The knowers and the practitioners of subtle science has gone beyond all the energy levels and thus came forward experiencing this force. The upanishads and the ancient texts work as the informative source. This paper works to analyse prana in upanishads. Here some important questions may be raised that Is there anything beyond the 'energy' explained by science? Is prana more than the energy inside the body? What is the relation of prana with universal prana?

Key words: Prana, Energy, Urja.

Introduction

Prana is generally translated as 'energy' or vital force. Energy is defined by science as quantitative property that is transferred to body or object. The science here refers to the physical energy but what is that carries the life? The vital word here means 'lively' or something without which one cannot live. This fact can only be understood through subtle science of yoga. The yogic texts, Vedic scriptures, samhita and Upanishads openly mention these theories on energy. Science is now somewhere moving towards experimenting the subtle energy. This subtle energy is 'prana' in sanskrit, 'Qi' in Chinese medicine and 'Ki' in Japanese. This origination of the word 'prana' can be clearly confirmed through our vedic texts. Hence, it is observed that subtle energy is not a new fact until it is self analysed and self experienced by an individual.

The experiences of the individual can differ in several basis, as emotional healing and the controllable of mind, for the fact that it is the pranic sheath that effects food sheath and mental sheath. The force of prana remains with us until our last exhale. Prana is so much related to our awareness and consciousness, several experiments have been already done in this aspect, so any time we draw our awareness to our physical region, we are filling it with prana. All beings have the prana present in them. The moment we pick a fruit from a tree, it starts losing its prana, so if we consume freshest of fruit grown locally, prana is at its peak.

In the words of Dr. Nagendra "Prana is the subtlest form of energy and energy is the grossest form of prana". This statement by him calls for not only classical analysis but also the experimental proof. He tries to inspire science to engage in the investigation of something subtler, more comprehensive, independent and powerful than energy.

What is Prana?

The whole universe can be comprehended in the terms of vibrations. The prana in its etymology प्र + अन् + अक् (denotes movement or vibration. It is the manifested vibration of pure consciousness. (ref:- **Adiurja prana, pg.7**) Modern science talks about various types of energy like electrical, thermal etc.

All these are the types of energies but these are expressions one, that surrounds one energy, namely cosmic energy. This energy surrounds the entire universe and express itself at different levels. According to the Upanishads whatever that exists in universe in the form of matter and energy are two aspects of one force.

These two aspects are named differently in different places. Some of the terms are: ray and prana, vyakta and avyakta, murta and amurta , surya and chandrama, dyo and prithvi etc. The Pransnupnishad highly give the knowledge of the pranic theory. In the words of Sri Aurobindo “ Prana or vital energy is present in every element or form, down to the atom ,because everywhere in essence and action,it is the consciousness only that is transferring its physical existence and is working secretly. It is the all-pervading ‘pranatatva’ which has manifested and resides in this world”(The life divine,vol.18,pg.187) The tantra shastras throwing light on the word prana says प्राणिनामुरसि स्थितः । The prana resides in the human heart and due to its vibrational energy it is called prana.

प्राणो वा इदं सर्वं भूतं यदिदं किञ्च ।)chndogya up. 3.15.4) Whatever is visible or invisible, movable or immovable, is in Prana, is through Prana. It is the manifested vibration of pure consciousness, which is eternal and ever-creative. Movement, light, creation and manifestation is through prana. It is a very subtle sound-vibration rising out of the silence of consciousness.

Prana in Upanishads

The upanishads are the set of philosophical religious texts, the central lessons of which have been regarded as the most fundamental elements of contemplative Indian religious sensibilities. The sanskrit word upanishad root sad means (“sit”) with prefixes upa and ni meaning (“nearby”) is understood that these texts originally, were lessons given to student sitting at the feet of learned master. The teaching of upanishads is about non-dual reality ,the oneness between the self and the brahman. Reality is one’s own self. The mind, the prana(vital force), momentary consciousness, the void(sunya), these have been held as reality. Prana has been the major significant concept in many upanishads. The word prana is used in the sense of every manifestation in the universe. The concept of prana taken in any aspect in vedas and upanishads is of deepest interest to man. It takes him to core of everything in the universe.

Origination of Prana

Prasna upanishad is the principle upanishad that unravels the secret of prana. In this the disciples ask questions to their guru, among which one of the disciple Kausalya ,son of Asvala asked rishi Pippalada,"भगवन् कुत एष प्राणो जायत"prasna up. 3/1)Sir, from where does this prana is born . “ आत्मन एष प्राणो जायत”The prana has originated from atman, answers the guru. The conscious, aware, energy, vibration etc are the synonyms used to describe prana. The prana comes from the atman itself. The veda and the shastras define atma as consciousness चैतन्यमात्मा । The nature of atman is being conscious - चैतन्यमात्मनो रूपम्) netratantra,8/28)

The Mundakopnishad mentions that , prana comes out of from the God himself. It is from the all power of God that the life force, all senses, bhutas, originate from it.

प्राणो वै ज्यष्ठश्च श्रष्ठश्च) | brihd up. 6.1.1)Prana is supreme and the first one to originate. It is believed that when God wanted to create universe, he took ‘sankalp’(बहु स्याम् प्रजयष्ट (to be many . And thus the prana is related to the determination of the supreme. तस्मिंल्लोकाः श्रिताः सर्वे तदु नात्यग्नि कश्चन ।(katha up. 2/3/1) Prana is the first birth. It is not generated from generated. It’s source is pure and luminous consciousness.

“The pulse or vibration that is generated in subtle nature by the union of the root nature and the all pervading consciousness is prana or vibration”. (shankarabhasya,brahmasutra 1.3.39)

Nature of Prana

The concept of energy in modern science is very useful in understanding the nature of universe. The law of conservation of energy says that energy can neither be created nor destroyed, it changes from

one form to another. It is a statement of fact that the quantity of energy remains constant regardless of its form and processes

Every form, the luminosity of motion and action is wholly united with prana, for this the prana itself is motion and action. Prana means the sublime movement. It is a paramount characteristic of this element which is controller of every movement of the dynamic world. Every study done on prana clarifies its nature, prana is immortal- “ प्राणो वा अमृतम्” (brihd up. 1.6.3)

Prana is force- “प्राणो वा बलम्”. (brihd up. 5.14.4) The upanishads and vedas define prana as everything, then it be shakti, atman and Brahman. But here we will understand prana on the aspect of ‘movement’ ‘path’ ‘procession’. Prana is the only element to which every theory is related. The knowledge on prana questions and gives a definite answer to every creation in the universe. Prana is global, stirring and incurable component. It is an eternal vibration -एक प्राण परिस्पन्दनः। (Muktikopnishad 2.48)

“The movement of this prana is independent and self transforming. Being originated from the ultimate independent consciousness, the prana is free and self-transforming.” (swachand up. 4/257)

In the words of Dr. Nagendra “ The energy is most basic spectrum of the physical world. It is because it has a minimal freedom. It changes its speed to any other direction, for this reason it needs an external person or reason. Prana can use its freedom efficiency at its expression level. At the expression level of mind, it can determine, take resolution and can also self transform” .

The tantra shastras mention this ‘movement’ as continuous vibration of para-shakti, which means ‘accent’ (Vigyan bhairav, 24). Prana is self manifesting source of all creation. It determines the nature, speed, power and action of every manifested object. This energy is active in every vibration of movement and transmission.

The Work of Prana

The prana in the body comes out of the ‘cosmic prana’. It gets distributed in the form of five vayus in the body. The energy whose play is the whole creation, is born out of atman. It covers the being just as the shadow spread over a body. It has no separate existence and therefore it is called maya.

As the emperor orders his officials, to be in different places, the chief prana engages other prana differently in their function. The upanishads mentions five pranas in the body, i.e. Prana, apana, samana, udana, vyana. Pransopnishad gives a clear understanding on this aspect.

यथा सम्राडेवाधिकृतान्विनियुङ्क्ते ।

एतान्प्रामानेता4/न्प्रामानधितिष्ठस्वेत्येवमेवैष प्राण इतरान्प्राणान्पृथक्पृथगेव सन्निधत्ते ॥3 -

The Apana is in the organs of excretion and generation; in the eye and the ear as well as in the mouth and the nose, dwells himself the Prana; and in the middle is Samana, as it distributes the offered food equally to all parts. From it originates the seven flames (two eyes, two ears, two nostrils, mouth).

In the heart dwells the Atman. There are (in the heart) a hundred and one nerves, in each of them there are a hundred, and each of these branch nerves again has seventy-two thousand nerves. In all these the Vyana moves. (3/6)

अर्थकयोर्ध्व उदानः पुण्येन पुण्यं लोकं नयति पापेन पापमुभाभ्यामेव मनुष्यलोकम् ॥

And then, through one of them the Udana carries (the soul) to the virtuous world by virtuous deeds, to the sinful world by the sinful acts, and by both to the world of men. (3/7)

The five pranas are responsible for creation and existence of an individual. Their physical location are relevant in regard to the function of body, however they function homogeneously in the subtle body. One should remember that the energy body it can also be understood through the realm of experiences. (Prasnaupanishad, Chapter 3)

<i>Prana</i>	<i>Physical</i>	<i>Subtle</i>
Prana	Thoracic region	Anahata to vishuddhi

Apana	Pelvic region	Swathisthana and mooladhara
Samana	between navel and diaphragm	Manipur
Udana	Organs of action and knowledge	Ajna and Sahasrara
Vyana	Whole body	Five koshas

Alongwith five major pranas there are five upa-pranas too- naga,koorma krikara,devadutta and dhananjay. The 'vayu' is more the physical word used by the commentators, therefore, the prana is something that is very subtle.

The Universal Prana

There are various description of creation in Upanishads. Some of them are, he created prana from prana faith, ether, air, light, water, earth, senses, mind and food. Here, everything comes out of the absolute reality itself. The chhdogya upanishad gives the statement regarding the supremacy, purity and superiority of the main prana (**Ch up. 1.2.1-9; brihad up. 1.3.1-8**)

The prana lacks attachment therefore it is pure and invincible. This prana, being away from death is known from far. Thus who knows the prana like this, is away from death.(**brihad up. 1.3.9**). At the cosmic level the prana, the supreme prana resides as immutable sound in the cosmic mouth at the individual level in the mouth as the main prana. This soul is invincible and is nectar. एवं ह वा एतमेषा देवता मृत्युमतिवहति य एवं वेद।(**ch up. 1.2.9**) The mahaprana is the prana which nourishes the other prana. Whatever this prana eats and drinks, it is feeded to other pranas.

This prana divide itself in five major pranas in the body. (**Mundak up. 3.1.9**). Why it divided itself? Because it is very powerful that it could not enter this body in his supreme oneness.(**Maitri up. 2.6**). When all the gods started showing their importance, then prana said – do not be tempted by life, it is I who divide myself into five parts and keeps this system of God stable (**Prasna up. 2.3**). When they did not believe, prana got angry, but when prana reverses then all reverses, when prana remains stable, all remains stable. (**Prasna up. 2.4**)

Prana is superior in every way. This is the axis to which all are united.(**Ch up. 7.15.1**)

Conclusion

Prana is the 'vital force' at individual level. It is the energy present in the physical, subtle and causal body. At the cosmic level, prana is behind the five elements. It is the universal energy, identical at microcosmic and macrocosmic level. The word prana is also used for 'brahman'.

The human body is made up of five elements. It is born out of the essence of food one eats. The food nourishes the body and creates a link between prana and the body. Prana keeps awake when the body, sense organs and mind goes to sleep. The word 'prana' can be understood and experienced in many form, but in body it comes from the maha prana. The maha prana is so powerful and supreme that it had to divide itself in the form of vayu in the body. Its supreme oneness could not enter the body. Therefore prana is the only one fact that is the base of creation of anything in the universe.

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